

Estimating the average duration of employment through predictive modeling to increase retention

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Abstract—Employee retention has become increasingly popular as the costs of turnover and competition for top talent continue to grow. This capstone project aims to analyze employee retention at an organization through a data-driven approach. We are investigating the factors influencing the retention and turnover of both full-time and part-time employees. For the purposes of this project, the word termination refers to an employee quitting their job voluntarily or getting fired. The objective of this project is two-fold: estimating the typical duration of employment for an individual based on other factors, and implementing techniques of survival analysis so the Human Resources department can take a more proactive approach to retaining employees. This study specifically utilizes data from the past three years containing information on demographics, job-related attributes, and evaluation metrics. The project conducts exploratory data analysis along with identifying different interactions among the existing variables to gain valuable insights and examine patterns. By predicting the average lifespan of an employee and identifying the variables that have the most influence on survival probability, the organization can enhance employee retention, therefore reducing possible costs associated with turnover, and maintaining a skilled and stable workforce.

Index Terms—Survival Analysis, Retention, Human Resources, data analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of this project is to evaluate employee retention by using predictive modeling to estimate the typical duration of employment, specifically referring to the length of time for an individual to be working for the organization. Our project looks to give our client an answer to the turnover patterns and how to predict if an employee will leave. Through diligent analysis of the provided data, it is possible to make conclusions about potential interactions of variables. The needs of the employees vary based on other attributes, however, the discovery of the main influencer factors can help our client implement targeted strategies to further improve workforce stability.

The targeted population of this project is the employees at our client's organization working full-time or part-time and contains information from the years 2020-2022. Our analysis involves looking at interactions between different variables along with the rate of terminations, using supervised machine learning algorithms like Linear and Logistic Regression models to predict specific outcomes for the employees, and conducting survival analysis to predict probabilities for employees leaving their jobs.

Section 2 of this paper provides a more thorough understanding of the background of this project along with relevant related work. In section 3, we have further discussed the data used for our project, including the ethical considerations, data preprocessing, and aggregations. Section 4 focuses on the methodology, describing the methods we have used to achieve our objectives, the challenges encountered, and the solutions given to those challenges. The results are in Section 5, with Section 6 being the Conclusion and suggestions for future work.

II. MOTIVATION

It is generally more expensive to hire a new employee than to retain a current employee. This has become even more important after the worldwide pandemic influenced more people to leave their jobs to spend more time with family. It has been reported that in 2020 replacing an employee would cost anywhere from one-half to two times their annual salary, and this was a conservative assessment. Around 4 million Americans quit their jobs in 2020, causing companies to lose significant amounts of financial resources [1].

To combat the increase in turnover, employers implement targeted retention strategies. Most of these include raising salary budgets, offering tuition reimbursement, providing off-cycle promotions with salary increases, allowing more remote days, and applying a wider emphasis on diversity, equity, and inclusion. However, these strategies also cost money for a company. Therefore, companies have turned to data-driven solutions such as predictive modeling and analysis to determine who is at risk of quitting and the causes for that, and if there are signs of an employee leaving [2].

The client for this project is the Human Resources department at an organization. Our secondary data are obtained from the organization's human capital management system. With the ever-changing job market talked about above, our client tasked us with estimating employee lifespan within their company in an effort to allocate resources most efficiently and effectively.

III. DATA

A. Ethical Considerations

Given the sensitive nature of the data encompassing employee demographics and job attributes, it was of high

significance for us to ensure ethical considerations and protect the integrity of our research, as well as all involved parties. In the earlier stages of our studies, we obtained the necessary permissions from the organization’s Human Resources department by signing a Confidential Capstone Data Use Agreement, stating that we carry full responsibility for the security of the data on our end. We have been careful not to disclose any sensitive information from our analysis that could harm the organization at any level. By thoroughly discussing and implementing an ethical approach, we aim to ensure this capstone project is conducted in a responsible and ethical manner, bringing value to our client without causing any trade-offs of compromise for the well-being of the participants of the organization involved. For the purposes of data integrity, details about our findings and variables will not be disclosed in our paper.

The portion of the data we were able to access was completely deidentified by our client. Attributes like employee names and dates of birth were replaced by a unique ID for each individual, and instead of addresses, more general geographic variables were presented. We do not have access to the linking between the employee IDs and their names and addresses, so we will not be able to connect the results of our analysis with that confidential information.

B. Data Aggregation

The data were provided by the Human Resources Department at the organization. The scope of the data includes demographics, job-related attributes, level of education, performance rating, and other relevant information about employees over the past three years, from 2020 to 2022. There were three separate datasets for each year, along with a separate file for terminations. The number of observations for the general data from 2020 was 240,179, decreasing to 235,032 for the 2021 data, which decreased further to 232,164 data points for the 2022 data. Each row in our dataset contains a snapshot of an employee at one point in time. Whenever there is an update to that employee’s pay, department, manager, or any record, another snapshot is added to the dataframe. The common identifier between the yearly snapshots and the termination dataset is the Employee ID, allowing them to be linked or merged as needed. We concatenated these three data files together to have one combined dataset containing all three years of data. The termination dataset includes information about a person’s EmployeeID, termination type, classified as voluntary, involuntary, and other involuntary, and the reason for termination. For the purposes of our analysis, we considered all types of terminations, including both voluntary and involuntary. We merged the termination dataset with our combined dataset using the EmployeeID field, to get our final comprehensive dataset, which resulted in 518,516 data points.

C. Data Cleaning

Out of the total 19 categorical variables, five contained ID information such as employee ID, jobID, ManagerID, and

three contained date information including HireDate, TerminationDate. For the purposes of keeping the analysis focused on a higher level, we removed all ID variables because we wanted our analysis to focus on the bigger, more categorical comparison across and between departments, rather than comparing specific job titles and managers. One of the variables contained the number of years the employee worked in a position, which allowed us to remove the start date variables. Any variables we deemed to be unnecessary, such as currency as it was all in USD, or redundant as there was another variable containing the same or more accurate information, were also removed. Finally, as mentioned earlier, to keep the focus of our analysis on a higher level, we removed all variables containing information on specific Job Titles or the specific reason for termination. Instead, we created a binary variable to represent termination.

In regards to the categorical variables, certain attributes had a large number of values such as CostCenterCode, HighestDegree, etc. For some of these, we were able to recode these by grouping together similar values to create more meaningful classes. For example, for Performance Rating we examined the 18 categories in the raw data and recategorized them based on the connotation of the ratings into positive, neutral, and negative. For HighestDegree, we transformed over 100 different values into seven, and Company into two based on the client’s recommendation. We performed similar groupings for a total of six categorical variables (Company, CostCenterCode, HighestDegree, JobFamilyGroup, Performance Rating, and Race). Utilizing a crosswalk we were provided, we were able to convert all of the old department codes to the correct cost center codes, which made the data consistent across all three years. Finally, we transformed three of the categorical variables to ordinal as their values had a natural hierarchical structure such as AgeGroup, HighestDegree, and PerformanceRating. We also made separate datasets where the remaining variables remained as is, or One-Hot, or dummy encoded. A visual representation of the data pipeline process explained thus far and including our future modeling steps is outlined below in *Figure 1*.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this capstone project, we utilize a comprehensive methodology to analyze the factors influencing employee retention, ensuring that our findings are based on rigorous research and data-driven insights. We initially implemented logistic regression with the binary response variable indicating whether an employee was terminated (1) or not terminated (0). Despite the very high accuracy score, the model was not very predictive due to the highly imbalanced nature of the data. In our dataset, 98% of the employees were not terminated, while only 2% were terminated, leading the model to consistently predict that an employee had not been terminated. As a result of this experiment, we recognized the importance of carefully considering class ratios in our further model development to prevent potential biases. To address the issue of imbalanced data, we decided to explore three approaches. Depending on

Fig. 1. Data Pipeline

the technique, we attempted modeling with either the full data, balancing our data through undersampling, or using only the subset of terminated employees in the data - which unfortunately reduced the data to only 2% of the original dataset but still provided a sufficient amount of data to work with.

Following this, we aimed to reduce the number of dimensions to mitigate the effect of multicollinearity. We explored Lasso, Ridge, ElasticNet, and Sparse PCA in Python with packages such as `glmnet`, `sklearn.linear_model`, and `matplotlib`. However, these approaches were found to be ineffective. Sparse PCA did effectively reduce our number of predictors, however, the results were not interpretable. Using the full dataset, Lasso failed to eliminate any predictors while Ridge and ElasticNet reduced all of the predictors to 0. In our

undersampled classification problem, we concluded that the variables were not effective for predicting our binary outcome of termination in our logistic regression.

As a result, we decided to shift our focus to another variable in our dataset: years in position. Instead of predicting whether or not an employee was terminated in a given snapshot, we could instead predict the average lifespan of an employee at a company. We switched to using Years In Position as our response variable for all subsequent models, hoping to achieve more meaningful and interpretable results.

A. Linear Regression

Our attempts to find patterns in our data led us to change the scope of our problem. Having in mind that every individual quits their job at some point for some reason, we decided to only focus on the persons that got terminated in our data, therefore analyzing the causing factors for termination from a machine learning modeling perspective. Furthermore, having the motive to predict the time when a given employee is at risk of termination, we decided to make our mission to predict the years in position for a given employee considering all the attributes of the person. As a result, we took a subset of our data from all three years where the termination variable had a value of 1, which was about 2% of our data with around 9,600 observations.

Since the outcome variable of years in position was a continuous value, we started off by building a linear regression model. The used packages for this section of our project were `pandas`, `numpy`, `seaborn`, and the modules `linear_model`, `model_selection` metrics, and `preprocessing` from the package `scikit-learn` in python. Our attempts of building our models with logged numeric features, implementing regularization techniques such as Ridge, Lasso, and ElasticNet, and using Grid Search Cross-Validation only resulted in severely overfitted models with low accuracy. Therefore, the ordinary least squares method with standardized numeric features was considered the best model among these.

B. Linear Model with Interaction Effects

After evaluating a linear regression model with transformations and focusing on the terminated data, we shifted to programming in R to reduce the dimensions and evaluate interactions between the predictors on as much data as possible. We started by using packages like `tidyverse`, `readr`, `dplyr`, and `leaps` to do stepwise regression on the entire dataset in both forward and backward directions. With this approach, we were hoping to systematically identify the most significant predictors and potential interactions. As a result, the only eliminated variable was the `zipcode`. In order to explore possible interactions, we decided to look at variables related to demographics, education, and job-related attributes. The six variables we chose to analyze interactions for included a combination of demographic variables, job-related attributes, and biographic variables. Utilizing `ggplot`, we created scatter plots for each pair of variables to evaluate the slopes of their respective classes as seen in Figures 2-7. When assessing these plots,

we wanted to ensure that the slopes were different enough to explain an interaction effect.

Fig. 2. Demographic1

Fig. 3. Demographic2

Fig. 4. Demographic3

Fig. 5. JobRelated1

Fig. 6. JobRelated2

Fig. 7. Bio1

With the exception of the variable Demographic3, all of the other variables had different slopes for each of their classes. Therefore, the variable Demographic3 was taken out of consideration for the remainder of the interaction analysis. We then utilized boxplots to compare every possible two-way combination of these variables. Consequently, we followed up with an anova test from the stats package to determine if each interaction was better than the original model with no interactions. Our significance level was $\alpha = 0.05$. The significant two-way interactions resulting from these tests are shown in Table 1.

	Demo1	Demo2	Job1	Job2	Bio1
Demo1	0	0	1	1	1
Demo2	0	0	1	0	1
Job1	1	1	0	1	1
Job2	1	0	1	0	1
Bio1	1	1	1	1	0

TABLE I
ANOVA TWO-WAY INTERACTIONS

We now conducted an ANOVA test between the full model with no interaction terms, and our model with the significant two-way interaction terms. Using a significance level of 0.05, this test revealed that the interaction effects were statistically significant. Using this full model with all interaction terms, we ran a backward stepwise regression. Stepwise regression normally does not include higher-order polynomial terms and interaction terms. However, by using the backward direction we were able to include our interaction effects and see if the regression would remove them. This regression eliminated all interactions with the exception of two pairings: Demographic 1 with Job-Related 2 and Job-Related 1 with Job-Related 2.

C. Survival Analysis

Utilizing the packages `condsurv`, `ggfortify`, `ggsurvfit`, `gt-summary`, `ROSE`, and `tidycmprsk`, we now turned to survival analysis. This method allowed us to determine the probability of an employee getting terminated at each point in time by year. We decided to run this model with our full dataset, using years in position as our response variable with whether or not they were terminated at each snapshot. Using the full data with no undersampling was necessary for this method to ensure we had data points with censoring. Censoring refers to the fact that termination is not observed for some employees by the “end” of our data. Our data only contains information up to the year 2022, so by that point we have partial information regarding terminations for certain employees. Employees will get terminated outside the scope of this data, but we do not have that information. We utilized a Cox Proportional Hazard regression model, which maximizes a partial likelihood function to account for censoring. Using the two-way interactions we discovered in the previous linear model, we fit the model with the years in position as response variable as mentioned above, and the same predictor variables as the former model. This outputted a survival curve that represented the probability of an employee being terminated each year along with the censored points.

We wanted to explore potential interactions in the same way we had in the linear model above. We started by generating survival curves of all the significant two-way interactions listed in Table 1. One of the variables in the table above had several different classes. However, in the scatterplot of this variable given in the figures above, we noticed that the lines fell into two groups. Following this natural distinction into two larger groups, we recoded this variable so that it now had two classes. The reasoning for this recoding was so that when we interacted it with the other variables, there were less lines to look at and we could see the larger picture, while still getting an accurate representation without losing the significance of the data. After generating all possible two-way interacted survival curves, we found that there were two pairs of interactions that were significant.

V. RESULTS

To assess the performance of each of our models, we utilized the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) as the evaluation

metric. It measures the error of each predicted outcome compared to the actual values, calculating the average of these errors, and then taking a square root of the result. Table 2 represents the results we were able to obtain from our three models.

Method	RMSE
<i>Linear Regression</i>	4.1544
<i>Linear with Interactions</i>	5.2800
<i>Survival Analysis</i>	9.8115

TABLE II
ROOT MEAN SQUARE ERROR

A. Linear Regression

After implementing multiple variations of regression models, such as Ridge, Lasso, ElasticNet, the best model we were able to achieve was a simple linear regression model with standardized numeric and outcome variables, with a root mean squared error of 0.93 for the scaled outcomes, and 4.15 for unscaled outcomes by years. The Ordinary Least Squares Regression model provided insights into the significance of different attributes. Analyzing the coefficients of this regression model findings indicate the relationship of specific attributes with time. For instance, considering a coefficient value of -0.5 for a specific feature, the interpretation would be that for every one-unit increase in the outcome variable—in our case, the number of years in position—the outcome variable is expected to decrease by 0.5 units, holding all the other variables constant [3].

Our findings indicate the most significant negative coefficient values come from one of the variables that describe job-related attributes. We were also able to identify 2 variables that have no influence on the outcome of our model. We observed some variables with multiple classes had patterns where some of the classes had positive coefficients, while other classes had a negative coefficients. Ultimately we found that there were 51 total significant variables, broken down into 45 categorical, 3 ordinal, and 3 numeric. Our analysis revealed that 22 variables were positively correlated with the outcome variable, and 29 variables were negatively correlated.

B. Linear Model with Interaction Effects

The final interaction model had the response variable as Years in Position, included thirteen total predictors and utilized undersampling for the data. This was broken down into two predictors being two-way interaction terms, three numeric predictors, and eight categorical predictors. As you can see in Table 2, the evaluation metric we used for each model was RMSE (root mean square error). The linear interaction model had a final RMSE of 5.2800 years. In application, this means our model’s predictions were off on average by about 5 years [4].

C. Survival Analysis

As stated above we evaluated several interactions and found two significant variable interactions in the survival curves. The

first was an interaction between Demographic 1 and Bio 1. We first plotted individual curves that looked closer at these variables individually, and then the joint interaction effect as seen in Figures 8, 9, 11. In the Demographic 1 curves, we see that initially Class 1 has a higher probability of survival compared to Class 2, however around the 35 year mark this flips to where Class 2 employees have a higher probability of survival. In the Bio 1 curves, the employees in Group A have a higher chance of survival. However, when looking at the combined interaction curves, note that Class 1 employees who are also in Group B have a higher probability of survival as compared to Class 2 employees who are also in Group A. This switches at the fifteen year mark, and around the 30 year mark, Class 2 employees who are also in Group B increase their probability of survival as compared to Class 1 employees who are also in Group B. The second interesting interaction we observed was between Job-Related 2 and Bio 1. Again we began by plotting the individual curves that looked closer at these variables individually, and then the joint interaction effect as seen in Figures 10, 12. In the Job-Related 2 curves, we see for the most part that the higher the level is for an employee, the higher their probability of survival. In the Bio 1 curves, the employees in Group A have a higher chance of survival. When looking at the combined interaction curves, note that the two groups with the highest probability of survival both were Level 3 employees. However, the third group with the highest survival probability, Level 2 employees who were also in Group A, switched with the Level 3 employees who were also in Group A. Additionally, Level 2 employees who were also in Group B, started out with the lowest survival probability as compared to Level 1 employees. At the 7 year mark, these Level 2 employees who were also in Group B switched to have higher survival probability as compared to the Level 1 employees who were also in Group B, and at the 13 year mark, this group switched with Level 1 employees who were also in Group A.

Fig. 9. Bio1

Fig. 10. JobRelated2

Fig. 8. Demographic1

Fig. 11. Demographic1 & Bio1

In Figure 13 below, it shows the final Cox Proportional Hazard curve with the final interaction model included in it.

Fig. 12. JobRelated2 & Bio1

As we can see people have a higher probability of staying in their job in the beginning of their career while at around 20 years there is a dip in the probability of an employee ‘surviving’ (staying). Lastly, at around 40 years the curve dips a lot more, decreasing the probability of an employee staying. Overall, looking at the curve there is a consistent decrease in probability as the years increase. Lastly, we again used the same evaluation metric for this model which had an RMSE of 9.8115 years. In application, this means our model’s predictions were off on average by about 9 years.

Fig. 13. Cox Hazard Proportional Model Curve

VI. CONCLUSION

Knowing the results of the several models we tried, we can conclude that our ordinary least squared regression model with standardized numeric features and outcome variable outperforms the other models making predictions. It results in an error of around 4 years, being significantly lower than the errors in the other models. In the future, we would recommend taking the idea of snapshots of the employees into consideration. More specifically, our data have a new observation for an employee every time changes occur in their profile, which resulted in having several repeated rows of the same employee ID; however these were considered as new employees in our data. This could be the cause of our high error in our models.

A. Future Work

Another option we explored was a Bayesian hierarchical model. We wanted to represent the interaction of gender and performance rating and how this can affect termination. The hierarchical model will have termination as the outcome instead of years in position. It also includes the full dataset as well as several of the variables from the linear model except for Job Family Group, Benefit Category group, and any interactions. We created a ‘Group’ variable that has 6 levels of the combination of the two classes of Demographic1 and three levels of Job-Related2. Something we want to point out about this Job-Related2 variable is that it is a sentiment analysis of the range of the raw data points. Further research could actually look into the scales that the Human Resources department uses. We recommend future work include this model to see if it can help predict when an employee will leave and the causing factors behind it.

Regarding horizontal comparisons, we think it would be interesting to explore the differences in terminations between departments. We recommend running a hierarchical model using the CostCenterCode variable (this is analogous to departments), to create different hierarchies. However, currently there are over one thousand unique cost center codes in this dataset, so we recommend grouping them into larger categories before running this model. A further step after running the hierarchical model for CostCenterCode comparison could be within each Cost Center, comparing the survival of employees across different job titles, which we removed earlier on in our analysis. Finally, we focused on termination as a binary, and removed the specific reasons for termination. Further categorizing the termination variable to account for these different reasons would also lead to meaningful regressions.

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